

Robust Brake Linings Friction Coefficient Estimation For Enhancement of EHB Control

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Abstract—The latest braking system architectures for Hybrid (HEV) and Full Electric Vehicles (EV) feature the adoption of the X-by-wire solutions, namely electro-hydraulic (EHB) and electro-mechanical (EMB) braking systems, aimed at providing additional flexibility to the distinctive functions of brake blending and regeneration. Regenerative brakes still need to be supported by conventional friction brakes because of failures occurrence, fully-charged battery conditions, and unexpected variations of the tire-road friction coefficient. In order to achieve a smooth coordinated action between the regenerative and the conventional friction brakes, the brake linings coefficient of friction (BLCF) needs to be monitored. The main contribution of this work lies on the estimation of the BLCF using a tire-model-less approach. In particular, two different observer designs are proposed and compared. Whereas the proposed approach does not rely on any fixed tire modelization, the state estimation is robust against variations in the road friction characteristics and tire uncertainties caused by inflating pressure variations, wear, and aging. The functionality of the developed observers is tested in *IPG CarMaker*[®] by employing an experimentally validated EV, equipped with four onboard motors and an EHB system. Braking events are simulated at different deceleration levels on both dry and wet surfaces. Finally, the compensation function against variations in the BLCF is implemented in the EHB controller to achieve constant deceleration levels. Authors envisage that the precise knowledge of the BLCF will contribute to enhance the braking performance and to actively monitor the brake pad wear under different working conditions.

Keywords—electro-hydraulic braking system; brake-by-wire; electric vehicle; tire-model-less approach; brake linings friction estimation

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the increasing stiffening of emission regulations has led the automotive industry to widen the fleet of EV and HEV. These vehicles include a plethora of innovative technologies known as X-by-wire solutions. The lack of a direct mechanical or hydraulic connection between the driver and the actuators ensures the control functions additional degrees of freedom. The electro-hydraulic brake system (EHB) [1], [2] has gained particular importance among the control community owing to the necessity of developing more and more sophisticated control systems for the enhancement of brake blending and regenerative functions [3]. Thanks to the brake-by-wire connection, the coordination between conventional and electric brakes occurs without the driver acknowledgment.

It is worth noticing that the control demand distribution of the blending function could incur failures that compromise the vehicle safety. To this regard, the compensation of external disturbances represents an important safety factor although it is still a poorly investigated topic among the research community. Rapid changes in road and environmental conditions, or external disturbances induced by variations in the Brake Linings Coefficient of Friction (BLCF), can lead to unpredictable vehicle behavior and deterioration of the braking performance and vehicle safety. Indeed, the knowledge of the BLCF plays a crucial role in the performance of braking control algorithms, since large deviations in the latter coefficient from the reference value employed in the controller can lead to undesirable deterioration of the brake control functions [4], [5].

Despite this, the caliper pressure has been typically used in literature to evaluate the brake torque, assuming a constant brake friction coefficient [6]. Unfortunately, a wide range of phenomena occurs between the brake pad and disc causing a remarkable variation of the BLCF: brake fading [7], [8], brake bedding [9], brake hysteresis against the pressure [10], brake hysteresis against the speed [11], brake wear [12] and aging [9], or dependence on the environmental conditions [13]. It is expectable that the knowledge of the BLCF will enable an optimal intervention control of the conventional brake by guaranteeing a seamless coordination with regenerative brakes and safe actuation of vehicle control systems such as ABS and ESP.

In this paper, the estimation of the BLCF is achieved using a tire-model-less approach. A major advantage with respect to previous model-based works [14] is the robustness of the proposed approach to changes in the road friction characteristics and variations in the tire parameters due to pressure, wear, and aging. In particular, two structures based on Stochastic Linear Kalman Filters are proposed: the first one relies on hub-force sensors that provide a direct measurement of the tire longitudinal forces [15]; the second one is based on the estimation of the tire longitudinal stiffness and longitudinal slip using standard signals available from the CAN bus of modern vehicles, measuring the real speed through GPS. An experimentally validated SUV-class vehicle model and two

Magic Formula 6.1 [16] tire models parameterized against dry and wet asphalt conditions [17] are used to assess the virtual sensors's performance in *IPG CarMaker*®. Moreover, experimental results from a brake dynamometric test rig have been implemented in an *Ostermeyer* [18] friction model to render the real evolution of the brake linings coefficient of friction. The results show that the observers reveal robust against variations in the road conditions and exhibit a remarkable tracking performance of the actual BLCF. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: In Section II relevant background regarding Kalman Filtering, the *Ostermeyer* friction model and the EHB system is presented. The state estimators proposed in this work are introduced in Section III. The analysis is conducted for the case of disabled regenerative brake in order to fully test the functionality of the proposed observer during base-brake maneuvers. Simulation results for dry and wet surfaces against different deceleration levels are provided in Section IV. Finally, conclusions and further research steps are discussed in Section V.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Kalman Filter

The state-space formulation is adopted to present the Linear Kalman Filter (*LKF*). Thus, a generic linear system can be expressed as follows (1- 2).

$$X_{k+1} = A_k X_k + B_k U_k + w_k \quad (1)$$

$$Y_{k+1} = C_k X_k + v_k \quad (2)$$

The terms w_k and v_k are the plant and measurement noises respectively, and it is assumed that these noises can be approximated by a zero mean uncorrelated Gaussian distribution: $w_k \approx N(0, Q_k)$; $v_k \approx N(0, R_k)$. The estimation process is computed in two steps. First, the time step prediction is performed using the plant model, (3). At the same time, an initial covariance matrix $P_{k+1|k}$ is computed based on the plant covariance noise Q_k , (4).

- Prediction:

$$\hat{X}_{k+1|k} = A_k \hat{X}_{k|k} + B_k U_k \quad (3)$$

$$P_{k+1|k} = A_k P_{k|k} A_k^T + Q_k \quad (4)$$

During the second step, the initial estimates $\hat{X}_{k+1|k}$ are corrected using the measurement vector Y_k and the Kalman gain K_{k+1} .

- Measurement correction:

$$K_{k+1} = P_{k+1|k} H_k^T [H_k P_{k+1|k} H_k^T + R_k]^{-1} \quad (5)$$

$$\hat{X}_{k+1|k+1} = \hat{X}_{k+1|k} + K_{k+1} [Y_k - H_k \hat{X}_{k+1|k}] \quad (6)$$

$$P_{k+1|k+1} = [I - K_{k+1} H_k] P_{k+1|k} \quad (7)$$

Finally, the relative importance of the process model (prediction step) or the measured variables (measurement correction) on the estimation is adjusted by the selection of the process and noise covariance matrices Q_k and R_k .

B. Model of the Brake System

The Ostermeyer model [18] is included in the vehicle dynamics simulation software *IPG CarMaker*® to reproduce the dynamics of the BLCF. The model has been previously calibrated against the experimental results obtained from a brake dynamometric test rig at the Technische Universität Ilmenau [19]. The model can be reliably used to simulate the onset of unexpected phenomena, among which the brake fading and brake hysteresis are the most relevant. Following the derivation presented in [18], the model relies on two differential equations in the friction μ and temperature T states, (8- 9).

$$\dot{\mu} = -[b(Nv + \epsilon)\mu - aT] \quad (8)$$

$$\dot{T} = -c[(T - T_0) - \gamma Nv] \quad (9)$$

Herein, it is worth remarking that the group Nv embeds the combined effect of the normal load and sliding speed, whilst the values of the constant parameters $a, b, c, \gamma, \epsilon$ are attributable to the pad chemical formulation. The initial brake temperature T_0 must be specified before the simulation starts in order to account for the initial brake thermal state.

C. Electro-hydraulic Brake System

The EHB system finds wide use in HEV and EV because ensures a smooth coordination between conventional and regenerative brakes without the driver acknowledgment. The EHB system employed in this work is depicted schematically in Fig. 1. The actuation is provided by means of the brake pedal, decoupled from the calipers. The brake pedal travel is measured and provided to the vehicle control unit (VCU). In accordance with the predefined brake pedal feel curves, the pedal simulator creates the required feedback force to the driver. Here, the VCU calculates the demanded brake pressure for each caliper and transfers the data to the electro-hydraulic control unit (EHCU). In turns, the EHCU realizes the actuation of wheel brake cylinders by setting the demanded pressure level in the wheel calipers through the proportional valves. The EHCU also controls the hydraulic pump to keep the accumulator over a certain pressure level. In the case of electric failure onset, the brake pedal still has a hydraulic connection with the system, and the brake system continues to operate in a fail-safe mode.

From several literature instances, it emerges that the decoupled brake system enables the compensation of different types of external disturbances [5]. Both long-term and short-term processes can take a toll on the blended control demand distribution and compromise the vehicle performance and safety. In this paper, the compensation function against variations in the BLCF is implemented in the EHCU to achieve constant deceleration levels. Such a tool can be employed to offset BLCF losses caused by phenomena arising after a series of brake applications (e.g. brakes warming-up and fading). The estimated BLCF is used in the VCU calculation procedure for the conversion of the brake torque demand to the pressure

Fig. 1. Half view of the Electro-hydraulic brake system [20].

demand. The compensation method will be further considered for the longitudinal braking mode.

III. OBSERVERS FOR BLCF ESTIMATION

In this paper, two filter architectures are proposed to estimate the brake pad friction coefficient, as reported in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Scheme of the developed observer architectures. Dash-dotted line refers to the observer Design 1; dashed line refers to the observer Design 2

A. Design 1: Direct measurement of the tire longitudinal forces

In the first design, it is assumed that the tire longitudinal forces can be measured directly by means of hub-force sensors [15]. The wheel rotating dynamics are modeled during braking

events by expression (10). Where I_w is the rotating inertia seen at the wheel frame, μ_{pad} is the linings friction coefficient to be estimated, K is a constant known parameter which depends on the brake caliper dimensions, p_{brk} is the braking pressure, which is modeled as a time-varying parameter, and r_e is the wheel effective radius. The rolling resistance factor is neglected for simplicity. Equation (10) is implemented in a Stochastic linear Kalman Filter, where the tire longitudinal force F_x and the brake pad friction coefficient are modeled as random-walk variables [21], [6], expressions (11-12),

$$I_w \dot{\omega} = -\mu_{pad} K p_{brk} - F_x r_e \quad (10)$$

$$\dot{F}_x = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$\dot{\mu}_{pad} = 0 \quad (12)$$

and the wheel angular velocity completes the vector of states (13).

$$X = \{\hat{\omega}, \hat{\mu}_{pad}, \hat{F}_x\} \quad (13)$$

Finally, the vector of measurements is formed by the wheel speed measured by standard ABS sensors and the longitudinal force provided by the hub-force sensors, expression (14).

$$Y = \{\omega_{meas}, F_{x,meas}\} \quad (14)$$

B. Design 2: Longitudinal velocity measured using a GPS

Despite hub-force sensors have been developed during the last years, the technology is still expensive and has not been implemented in production vehicles at the moment. A cost-effective solution suitable for current production vehicles is proposed in this section. Specifically, the direct measurement of the longitudinal forces is replaced with a virtual sensor that relies on readily available measurements (wheel speed, longitudinal acceleration) and GPS signals [22]. Additional considerations regarding the final implementation of the observer (e.g. influence of the GPS signal frequency) will be addressed in the future. If the braking action occurs within the tire linear region limits, the longitudinal force can be approximated by expression (15),

$$F_{x,vs} = \hat{\lambda} \hat{C}_\lambda \quad (15)$$

where $\hat{\lambda}$ denotes the estimated longitudinal slip, and \hat{C}_λ is the estimated tire longitudinal stiffness. Assuming that measurements of the “true” vehicle longitudinal velocity V_{meas} are provided by a GPS system, the tire longitudinal slips can be estimated during straight-line driving by expression (16),

$$\lambda = \frac{V_{meas} - r_e \omega}{V_{meas}} \quad (16)$$

where the ISO slip convention has been adopted [16]. In order to reduce the influence of the noise on the estimated longitudinal slip, expression (16) is solved and $\hat{\lambda}$ is obtained

using Recursive Least Squares (RLS) [17]. Moreover, the observer is switched off if the vehicle velocity is below a predefined threshold in order to avoid large inaccuracies on the estimated longitudinal slip [17]. The formulation of the RLS algorithm is omitted here due to space limitation. For further details, [23] can be consulted. If the braking action is performed within the linear region limits (i.e. wheel lock does not occur), and an even surface is considered for simplicity, the vehicle longitudinal dynamics can be approximated by the force balance expression (17).

$$ma_{x,meas} = \sum C_i \lambda_i - F_{aero} \quad (17)$$

With $i \in \{FL, FR, RL, RR\}$. Moreover, if the aerodynamic drag is disregarded, and a symmetric lateral braking action is considered (which is a reasonable assumption for regular braking events) expression (17) can be simplified as (18).

$$ma_{x,meas} = C_{\lambda_f} \lambda_f + C_{\lambda_r} \lambda_r \quad (18)$$

Taking into account the load proportionality principle [24], [6], [25], the tire longitudinal stiffness can be expressed as a function of the tire vertical load ($C = \frac{F_z}{F_{z0}} C_0$), where C_0 is the tire longitudinal stiffness at nominal load (F_{z0}). If the rear longitudinal stiffness is expressed as a function of the front longitudinal stiffness, the following expression (19) can be formulated:

$$C_{\lambda_r} = C_{\lambda_f} \frac{\hat{F}_{zr}}{\hat{F}_{zf}} \quad (19)$$

Eventually, the longitudinal stiffness can be calculated from the measured longitudinal acceleration, longitudinal slips, and tire vertical loads, equation (20).

$$C_{\lambda_f} = \frac{ma_{x,meas}}{(\lambda_f + \lambda_r \frac{\hat{F}_{zf}}{\hat{F}_{zr}})} \quad (20)$$

The tire vertical loads (F_{zf}, F_{zr}) are approximated using a quasi-static longitudinal weight transfer approach [24], [25], expression (21),

$$\hat{F}_{z,j} = F_{z0,j} \pm \beta a_{x,meas} \quad (21)$$

with $j \in \{front, rear\}$ and β denoting a constant coefficient that depends on the chassis mass and geometry. The estimated longitudinal stiffness \hat{C}_{λ_f} is obtained applying RLS to expression (20). Finally, the virtual force is computed from equation (15), and the rest of the state estimator structure used in the first design is maintained, being the vector of measurements of the first design replaced by the vector (22).

$$Y = \{\omega_{meas}, F_{x,vs}\} \quad (22)$$

IV. RESULTS

A. Observer Evaluation

The observers presented previously were implemented in *IPG-CarMaker*® and tested in accordance with the catalog of maneuvers described in Tables II. In accordance with literature instances dealing with braking investigation procedures, the discrimination between service and emergency braking stems from the brake pedal actuation velocity. Hereto, high values of the pedal actuation velocity ($> 100mm/s$) induce emergency braking manoeuvre; otherwise low values ($< 20mm/s$) produce service braking [20]. A fixed time step of $1ms$ was set during the simulations and the signals required by the observers were acquired at $100Hz$ using a zero-order hold. An additive noise model was employed to incorporate white Gaussian noise into the simulation signals [17]. The standard deviation values of the noise were extracted from datasheets of state-of-the-art instrumentation [26], [27]: $\sigma_{v_x} = 0.027 m/s$; $\sigma_{\omega} = 0.062 rad/s$; $\sigma_{F_x} = 10 N$; $\sigma_{a_x} = 0.01 m/s^2$. Experimentally validated models of a *SUV*-class vehicle and tire *MF 6.1* [16], [17] were employed during the simulations, Table I. The *EHB* brake system was implemented in *IPG-CM*® and a fixed braking torque distribution, namely 80/20, was set as with previous works [17], [22]. A more elaborate non-constant braking torque distribution will be implemented in the future.

TABLE I
VEHICLE MODEL EMPLOYED DURING THE SIMULATIONS

Vehicle Type	SUV-class electric vehicle
Total Vehicle Mass	2000 kg
Powertrain type	AWD
Drivetrain type	Individual Onboard Electric Motors
Braking System type	Decoupled electro-hydraulic
Tire size	245-40/R19

TABLE II
CATALOG OF MANEUVERS. SB* SERVICE BRAKING, EB* EMERGENCY BRAKING

Test	V_0 (kph)	Grip	a_x (m/s^2)	μ_{pad} comp.
#1 SB	120	Dry	3 – 5	N
#2 EB	120	Dry	6 – 8	N
#3 SB	120	Wet	3 – 5	N
#4 EB	120	Wet	6 – 8	N
#5 SB	120	Dry	3 – 5	Y

Initially, the *EHB* braking system was simulated in *over-braking* mode, assuming a constant brake pad friction coefficient ($\mu_{pad} = 0.2$). The vehicle is driven at a constant speed ($120kph$) during one second, and after that, a step braking input is applied. Results corresponding to the first test, service braking in dry conditions, are depicted in Fig. 3.

Expectedly, best results are seen on the observer based on direct measurements of the longitudinal forces (*Obsv. 1*). The friction coefficient of the brake pads is estimated accurately upon the braking maneuver is initiated and follows precisely the evolution dictated by the *Ostermeyer* model. Concerning

Fig. 3. Test #1. Service braking on dry road. (a) Velocity, (b-c) Front-Rear brake pad friction coefficient, (d) Long. acceleration, (e-f) Front-Rear long. force.

the estimation using the observer based on low-cost measurements, both the brake pad friction and the longitudinal force estimations are remarkable. Some noise is noticed on the rear axle estimates due to the low excitation level. In addition, a slight delay caused by a non-optimal tuning of the filter is observed in the μ_{pad} signals provided by the *Obsv. 2* (red-dashed trace). An improvement of the dynamic response of the observer will be pursued in the following research steps by employing meta-heuristic optimisation [28].

Fig. 4. Test #2. Emergency braking on dry road. (a) Velocity, (b-c) Front-Rear brake pad friction coefficient, (d) Long. acceleration, (e-f) Front-Rear long. force.

The results of the second test, aggressive braking on a dry road, are presented in Fig. 4. In this case, a slight offset appears on the estimate of the rear longitudinal force provided by the second observer. The load proportionality principle is compromised in this test due to the severe longitudinal weight transfer, thus affecting the accuracy of the rear brake pad friction estimate. Despite this, the error remains within reasonable values and can be considered acceptable.

The results obtained in the third test (service braking on a wet road) are omitted as significant differences with respect to the first test were not identified. Finally, the results of the aggressive braking input on a wet road are depicted in Fig. 5. As can be seen in Fig. 5, the performance of the second

Fig. 5. Test #4. Emergency braking on wet road. (a) Velocity, (b-c) Front-Rear brake pad friction coefficient, (d) Long. acceleration, (e-f) Front-Rear long. force.

observer is affected by the wheel-lock occurring at the end of the test ($t \approx 4 - 5$). During these situations, *Obsv. 2* might be switched off until the wheel-lock is reduced and the braking force linear region is revisited.

B. BLCF compensation

Previous works have shown that deviations of the brake pad friction coefficient from the reference value employed in the controller can lead to undesirable deterioration in the brake control functions [4], [5]. This section puts forth the results obtained in case the BLCF compensation function is implemented in the EHCUC. As already mentioned, the compensation function provides a smooth constant braking deceleration based on the brake pedal position, thus improving the comfort and braking linearity.

A service braking manoeuvre ($a_{x,demand} \approx 4m/s^2$) was induced on dry conditions and the results depicted in Fig. 6 were obtained. Overall, the included function is able to compensate the BLCF increase and modulates the braking pressure to maintain a constant braking torque, thus ensuring a constant longitudinal deceleration.

Fig. 6. Test #5. Service braking on dry road. (a) Long. deceleration, (b-c) Front-Rear braking torque.

Despite an initial overshoot is noticed when the *Obsv. 2* is employed, the deceleration level is maintained constant with minimum deviations.

To conclude, the accuracy of the observers was quantified by means of the Root Means Square *RMS* estimation error, [6], [29] and its outcomes are presented in Table III.

TABLE III
RMS ERROR OF THE OBSERVERS.

Test	Obs.	$e_{\mu_{pad,FL}}$	$e_{\mu_{pad,RL}}$	$e_{F_x,FL}$	$e_{F_x,RL}$
#1	Obs. 1	0.012	0.022	10.58	9.76
	Obs. 2	0.011	0.034	177.31	144.58
#2	Obs. 1	0.010	0.019	16.36	9.73
	Obs. 2	0.011	0.028	302.18	193.46
#3	Obs. 1	0.012	0.022	10.58	9.76
	Obs. 2	0.012	0.040	198.19	166.17
#4	Obs. 1	0.010	0.019	18.56	9.74
	Obs. 2	0.010	0.037	295.10	254.24
#5	Obs. 1	0.013	0.024	12.12	10.47
	Obs. 2	0.012	0.039	147.54	121.99

Overall, the error of the BLCF estimate remains within reasonable limits. Surprisingly, important differences are not noticed between observers, indicating the advisability of the low-cost observer (*Obsv. 2*) in case of service braking occurrence. Higher error values are observed with reference to the rear axle due to low levels of longitudinal excitation.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a novel tire model less approach based on the Linear Kalman filter has been put forth for the estimation of the BLCF. Specifically, two observer configurations drawing upon respectively expensive hub-force measurement devices and standard low-cost sensors have been proposed. Simulations have been carried out on dry and wet roads by incorporating assessed experimental data in the *IPG-CarMaker*®. Results demonstrate the suitability of the low-cost state observer for providing an accurate estimation of the BLCF in the case of braking inputs confined in the tire-road force linear region. Moreover, the developed tool is used to enable the BLCF compensation function in the *EHCUC*. As expected, a constant deceleration level based on the driver demand is achieved.

The evaluation of the system under non-constant braking torque distribution and the experimental validation of the observers will be pursued in the next steps of this research. Among the prospective applications, the proposed tool will be used to attain a more efficient use of the frictional brakes and to support a brake controller aimed at minimizing the pad wear volume.

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